
Goals and action plan 2026
*National Strategy for Data Management
based on the FAIR Principles*

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Terminology/acronym	Description
CISO	Chief Information Security Officer Forum
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DeiC	Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
DM	Data Management
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
maDMP	Machine actionable Data management plan
NCC	National Competence Center
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDM	Research Data Management

1. Introduction

This action plan is one of a series of deliverables under the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles¹. New readers are encouraged to visit Zenodo² for detailed insights into the timeline of the strategy.

The working groups

The FAIR Reference Group has established several working groups to track and advance focus areas in the FAIR strategy. At the launch of the strategy in 2022, five working groups were activated alongside the FAIR Reference Group. Since then, an additional working group (Valuation of Data) has been established, reflecting the evolving priorities of the strategy.

Toward the end of 2025, Working Group E – *Security Aspects of FAIR Data Collaboration* – proposed to the FAIR Reference Group to consolidate its activities with the CISO forum (Chief Information Security Forum). As the members of Working Group E are largely drawn from CISO Forum, which meets regularly and addresses overlapping and complementary topics, this proposal was considered as an opportunity to streamline efforts and enhance alignment. Consequently, it was agreed that security-related contributions to the FAIR strategy will continue through CISO Forum, rather than as a separate working group within the strategy. To ensure continuity and strong coordination, a member of the FAIR Reference Group has been appointed as the liaison between CISO Forum, the FAIR Reference Group, and the remaining working groups.

The working groups of 2026:

1. Working group A: Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management
With special attention to focus areas 1, 2, and 3
2. Working group B: Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation
With special attention to focus areas 4, 5 and 6
3. Working group C: Financial plan for FAIR data
With special attention to focus areas 7, 8
4. Working group D: Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge
With special attention to focus areas 9, 10, 11, and 12
5. Working group F: Valuation of data
With special attention to focus area 13

Addendum for 2026

In 2025, the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science (UFS) decided to continue the work on the FAIR Strategy through the end of 2026. The national FAIR strategy now operates under a rolling mandate, whereby UFS will review the continuation of the work on an annual basis.

Rather than issuing a new remit for 2026, an addendum³ has been prepared to provide flexibility and to outline guidelines for the action plans for 2026. This addendum supplements the Terms of Reference for the FAIR Reference Group 2023–24⁴, which was extended until the end of 2025, and builds on the progress achieved to date in implementing the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles.

¹ National FAIR-Strategy <https://www.deic.dk/da/data-management/National-FAIR-strategi>

² Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation 2022 and Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation, second mandated period (from 2023)

³ Addendum to the Terms of Reference for the FAIR Reference Group in 2026

⁴ Remit and Terms of Reference for the Reference group for the implementation of the National Strategy for Data Management Based on the FAIR Principles

To support the continued and adaptive development of action plans, the addendum introduces the following guidelines:

- The focus areas may be adjusted, if relevant, as a consequence of the results from previous reports.
- Focus areas that are no longer deemed relevant may be recommended for closure
- Knowledge sharing with university leadership or other relevant stakeholders is given increased attention, including via an annual meeting for the FAIR Reference Group and all the working groups.
- Consider developing a concrete monitoring mechanism to measure progress in implementing the strategy, which can be used in communication with leadership and others.

Accordingly, the focus areas defined for 2026 reflect this adaptive approach. Some areas remain unchanged from the existing Terms of Reference, while others have been concluded, or reformulated. As a result, the numbering of focus areas has changed from those of the Terms of Reference⁵.

Focus areas 2026

With reference to the Addendum for 2026 and the FAIR reference group's remit and terms of reference, the focus areas for 2026 include:

1. How do different disciplines implement the FAIR principles in research practices? For example, in their specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from/in collaboration with international research environments.
2. What policies and motivating/supportive measures exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?
3. Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing overall data responsibility, even after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ceased.
4. What infrastructure is available for the long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how is coherence and collaboration ensured between research institutions, DeiC, and the National Archives regarding long-term preservation?
5. How can services for data management planning continue to be developed nationally and internationally, and how can data management plans be made machine-readable, and be used in connection with the submission of research data to the National Archives?
6. How can controllers of data maintain their data-protection obligations while granting responsible use of data for research? How can infrastructure support this, and what is required to make the process trusted and seamless across digital research environments?
7. How can the funding agencies support universities' work with FAIR principles in relation to processes and policies?
8. How are relevant costs for FAIR data management covered?

⁵ Focus areas 8, 14, 15 and 16 from 2025 are in 2026 considered closed.

9. What competence profiles have research institutions established for the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers? How have research institutions built the data stewardship research support function for researchers?
10. To what extent is there interest in developing and offering the research support function collectively, at the national level? For example, under a central or decentralised national competence center.
11. Is there interest among research institutions in national coordination of educational offerings (not research support) within FAIR research data management? Can a potential national collaboration aim at division of labor, specialisation, and joint national offerings of educational programs, such as through a competence center under the auspices of DeiC? This includes education at all levels, from bachelor to further education of scientific staff.
12. How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally for FAIR data management practices at research institutions?
13. What criteria for a dynamic value of data as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context are applied by local, national, and international organisations to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

Based on the above-mentioned focus areas, the working groups have proposed goals and actions that they consider essential to address.

The FAIR Reference Group has also chosen to place emphasis on communication – both as a tool for internal collaboration between working groups and as a means of establishing a national framework for easily accessible and understandable information about the FAIR strategy and its implementation. Communication with both users and decision-makers is considered especially important, as the digitalisation of research and the national implementation of the FAIR principles represent one of the most significant practice and cultural shifts the research community has experienced in recent times.

2. Deliverables 2026: The FAIR Reference group

Timeline	Deliverable	Elements
March 2026	Action plan for the goals and deliverables for 2026 is submitted to The Agency for Higher Education and Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Input to the action plan has been received from the working groups • The action plan is completed and submitted to the Agency for Higher Education and Science • Communication efforts have been planned
June 2026	Status meeting with the working groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status on collected data and activities • Status on communication with individual universities and other relevant institutions
December 2026	Annual report is submitted to The Agency for Higher Education and Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status of the cross national activities received from all working groups • Annual report is completed and sent to The Agency for Higher Education and Science

3. Deliverables 2026: The working groups

Timeline	Deliverable	Elements
Deliverable march 2026	Action plan for the goals and deliverables for 2026 is submitted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify goals, actions, and prioritise the focus areas of the working group.
Deliverable mid 2026	Status meeting with the FAIR reference group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status on collected data and activities. Follow-up on the action plan and plans for additional efforts in 2026
Deliverable ultimo 2026	Contribution to the annual report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of the cross-national activities outlined in the working group's terms of reference.

4. Goals & actions supporting communication

Internal and external communication:

Goal 0.1. Communication support is established across the 6 working groups, where members can access information about:

- Policies
- Strategies
- Tools
- Manuals
- International references
- Litterature
- Courses related to FAIR and Data Management
- ...

Action 0.1: Communication channels are established for the working groups on Microsoft Teams, where members can access information about the above, save agendas, minutes, and other documents, and communicate internally.

Goal 0.2: A channel for public publishing of relevant material from the working groups and the FAIR Reference group is established.

Action 0.2: A channel on Zenodo⁶ is created for the FAIR strategy, mandate period 2023-2025.

⁶ <https://about.zenodo.org> Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation, second mandated period (from 2023)

5. Premises of the working groups

This section has been added by the working groups, to provide an overview of the premises that need to be in place for the action plan to be successfully implemented.

- Management support from the FAIR Reference group to prioritise this work at the individual universities
- Prioritisation and dedicated time from the members of working groups
- Dedicated partners/contacts from all the universities, who have the possibility to prioritise this work
- Coordination of resources among the FAIR working groups, so certain individuals/groups at the universities are not overloaded
- The working groups will develop material of guiding/observational nature, while it will be up to the FAIR Reference group to assess the extent to which the universities would fulfill the recommendations, and whether or not to follow up on them.

6. Goals & actions: Working group A

Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management

Working Group A has developed proposals for actions addressing the following focus areas:

Focus area 1

How do different disciplines implement the FAIR principles in research practices? For example, in their specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from/in collaboration with international research environments?

Goals:

Achieve a broader understanding of the implementation of FAIR practices in different disciplines.

Actions:

Expand the 2025 report with one or more examples from the humanities/social sciences. Possibly include examples from foreign data stewardship collaborations.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

To be completed in October 2026.

Focus area 2

What policies and motivating/supportive measures exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?

Goals:

Shed light on how policies and support have evolved since the national FAIR strategy was published in 2021.

Actions:

Update the 2025 report and describe the progress since the previous report and since the publication of the national FAIR strategy in 2021. Ask the universities what they consider to be the biggest advances at their institution in FAIR data management, and what they consider to be missing.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

To be completed in October 2026.

Focus area 3

Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing overall data responsibility, even after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ceased.

Goals:

Provide examples of best practices and policies for data governance.

Actions:

Expand section 4 of the 2025 report with a detailed set of best practices and examples of data governance at the universities. Describe onboarding and offboarding procedures and how to introduce new scientists to good data management.

Monitoring progress, including a time

To be completed in October 2026

7. Goals & actions: working group B

Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long-term preservation

Working group B proposes the following action plan for 2026 but reserves the right to adjust it in light of its findings.

Working Group B has developed proposals for actions addressing the following focus areas:

Focus area 4

What infrastructure is available for the long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how is coherence and collaboration ensured between research institutions, DeiC, and the National Archives regarding long-term preservation?

Goals:

Using the three preservation classes identified in its earlier work, the group will examine the data lifecycles associated with each class and the interactions between them.

Actions:

- Using data lifecycles associated with each of the three preservation classes to identify interactions and dependencies between them.
- Formulate recommendations for data infrastructures that can effectively support these lifecycle requirements.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The above actions are expected to be carried out continuously throughout 2026.

Focus area 5:

How can services for data management planning continue to be developed nationally and internationally, be made machine-readable, and be used in connection with the submission of research data to the National Archives?

Goals:

Machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) are tightly linked to, and constrained by, the tools and infrastructures they are intended to manage. The group will review current developments in the use of maDMPs at both local and international levels to assess the maturity of the associated tools and their adoption.

Furthermore, the group will track and analyse usage statistics of Danish DMP services from 2023 to 2026 to identify development patterns and adoption trends.

Actions:

- Review current developments in the use of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) in both Danish and international contexts.
- Assess the maturity of the methods, standards, and infrastructures that support the creation and execution of maDMPs.
- Analyse usage statistics from Danish DMP services for the period 2023–2026 in order to identify patterns of development and adoption.
- Identify gaps between the intended capabilities of maDMPs and the current maturity of supporting tools and infrastructures.

- Formulate recommendations for infrastructure supporting machine-actionable Data Management Plans.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The above actions are expected to be carried out continuously throughout 2026.

Focus area 6

How can controllers of data maintain their data-protection obligations while granting responsible use of data for research? How can infrastructure support this, and what is required to make the process trusted and seamless across digital research environments?

Reformulation of action area 6:

The working group, drawing on the group's expertise, has decided to reformulate the action area from:

Elaborate on how research institutions work with security infrastructure (Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure, AAAI) specifically and especially for sensitive data, with the aim of also making these FAIR.

To:

How can controllers of data maintain their data-protection obligations while granting responsible use of data for research? How can infrastructure support this, and what is required to make the process trusted and seamless across digital research environments?

This revised formulation allows the group to focus on how infrastructures can enable more seamless data-management practices. It better aligns with the group's competencies and expertise and has the potential to provide valuable insights into the requirements for trust in the Danish research infrastructure.

Goals:

The group aims to analyse responsible processes and governance frameworks for defining and managing access to potentially sensitive data within specific data domains. This includes reviewing implemented governance models and practices at both national and international levels. The group will develop practical guidance to support data controllers in upholding their security and data-protection obligations while enabling appropriate and lawful access when needed. In addition, it will define how digital research infrastructures can facilitate compliant, secure, and efficient data access and reuse.

Actions:

- Review and analyse selected national and international governance models for managing access to potentially sensitive data.
- Analyse the legal and organisational constraints faced by data controllers when enabling the use of sensitive or regulated data for research.
- Identify key challenges and success factors in balancing data-protection obligations with research access.
- Formulate recommendations for infrastructure and governance models that enable responsible research use of data while maintaining data-protection obligations.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

The above actions are expected to be carried out continuously throughout 2026.

8. Goals & actions: Working group C

Financial plan for FAIR data

The Working Group's Approach to Implementing FAIR

Working Group C assumes that the FAIR principles should be implemented in an administratively *lean* manner, respecting researchers' time and resources as much as possible. The effort should create real value for researchers and support their core tasks—not impose unnecessary administrative burdens.

Implementation must therefore not come at the expense of research resources but should be based on clear guidelines, relevant tools, and targeted administrative support.

Working Group C has developed proposals for actions addressing the following focus areas:

Focus area 7

How can the funding agencies support universities' work with FAIR principles in relation to processes and policies?

Reformulation of Focus Area 7:

In 2025, the working group prepared the document [Forslag til praksis vedrørende FAIR for statslige fonde](#) (*Proposals for Practices Regarding FAIR for Governmental Funding Agencies*). The document contains recommendations on how governmental funding agencies can establish practices that support research institutions and researchers in achieving FAIR compliance, particularly in relation to data management plans (DMPs).

Based on this work, the working group considers that the previous formulation of the focus area is no longer adequate:

EU programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) require grant recipients, in connection with applications, to prepare data management plans. To what extent can national research funding agencies benefit from following this practice?

The focus area is therefore reformulated as:

How can the funding agencies support universities' work with FAIR principles in relation to processes and policies?

Goals:

Building on the above-mentioned document from the working group and the updated [Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), the working group will examine whether the recommendations can be further developed and potentially supplemented with common guidelines for governmental funding agencies.

Actions:

1. The working group will revise the existing recommendations and/or supplement them with a draft of a common guideline for governmental funding agencies.
2. The draft will be circulated for consultation with the funding agencies and universities.
3. The recommendations will be tested in practice at selected funding agencies and universities.

4. Feedback from the testing phase will be collected and processed, after which the draft may be adjusted.

Monitoring Progress, Including Timeline:

Actions 1 and 2 will be carried out in Q2 2026.

Actions 3 and 4 will be carried out in Q3 and Q4 2026.

Focus area 8

How are relevant costs for FAIR data management covered?

Reformulation of Focus Area 8:

Based on the working group's work in 2024 and 2025, it is assessed that the focus area can better be clarified and reformulated from:

Which costs for data management can be included in budgets?

to:

How are relevant costs for FAIR data management covered?

Goals:

The working group has reviewed the [Agreement on a Common Model for Financing Research Projects](#)⁷, concluded by Danish universities and six private foundations, and analysed the extent to which expenses for data management (DM) are included in the agreement. The results of this review are presented in the 2024 annual report and were further developed in 2025 with a focus on different types of DM-related needs.

The working group assesses that there is still a need for a more concrete and detailed knowledge base regarding data management costs. On this basis, the working group will collect examples from universities and foundations of various types of research projects to identify specific DM-related costs and analyse how these costs have been covered.

Actions:

- Collect examples from universities and foundations of data management costs in different types of research projects.
- Clarify and define what is understood as data management in a cost context (e.g., preservation, documentation, access, and any salary expenses for data managers).
- Analyse the relationship between data management costs and:
 - project size
 - project duration
 - data types (e.g., sensitive or personally identifiable data)
 - salary costs related to data management
- Prepare an overview (e.g., in table form) with an estimate of costs distributed across different data types.
- Describe selected examples of good practices (cases).

Monitoring Progress, Including Timeline:

The above actions are expected to be carried out continuously throughout 2026.

⁷ The agreement is written in danish: *Aftale om en fælles model for finansiering af forskningsprojekter*

9. Goals & actions: working group D

Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

Working group D has clustered the focus areas and related actions into three topics: (1) Data Stewardship, (2) National Competence Center, and (3) Recognition and Reward of FAIR Data Management. Working Group D has developed proposals for actions addressing the following focus areas:

(D1) Data Stewardship

Focus area 9

What competence profiles have research institutions established for the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers? How have research institutions built the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers?

Goals:

1. Consolidated description of the current Danish data stewardship landscape
2. Recommendations for how institutions can staff and organise data stewardship support functions
3. Recommendations for how national coordination and shared offerings could support local initiatives and strengthen capacity across institutions

Actions:

1. Conduct focus groups and semi-structured interviews with selected respondent groups to supplement the 2025 national survey results
2. Consolidate findings into concrete recommendations for staffing and organising data stewardship support at Danish universities
3. Align the identified professional profiles and skills gaps with European skills frameworks to identify opportunities for national coordination and shared offerings

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

1. Milestone M1.1 (June 2026): Focus groups and semi-structured interviews completed; preliminary analysis
2. Milestone M1.2 (September 2026): Analysis completed; draft recommendations prepared
3. Milestone M1.3 (November 2026): Final recommendations report submitted

(D2) National Competence center

Focus area 10

To what extent is there interest in developing and offering the research support function collectively at the national level? For example, under a central or decentralised national competence center.

Focus area 11

Is there interest among research institutions in national coordination of educational offerings (not research support) within FAIR research data management? Can a potential national collaboration aim at division of labor, specialisation, and joint national offerings of educational programs, such as through a competence center under the auspices of DeiC? This includes education at all levels, from bachelor to further education of scientific staff.

1. Consolidated description of different scenarios for a potential Danish NCC
2. Overview of institutional needs and interests in relation to creating a National Competence Center for FAIR Data Management in Denmark,
3. Overview of institutional needs and interests regarding national coordination of FAIR data management education and training

Actions:

1. Design and conduct focus groups and interviews to clarify whether a Danish NCC is desirable, which service functions could meaningfully be centralised at the national level, and whether national coordination of FAIR/RDM education and training is a suitable alternative to current practice
2. Map opportunities for national coordination activities

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

1. Milestone M2.1 (June 2026): Needs assessment design completed; stakeholder consultations conducted
2. Milestone M2.2 (September 2026): Consultations and analysis completed; draft options prepared
3. Milestone M2.3 (November 2026): Report with options for a Danish NCC submitted to the FAIR Reference Group

(D3) Recognition and Rewarding regarding FAIR Data Management**Focus area 12**

How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally for FAIR data management practices at research institutions?

Goals:

1. Mapping of current institutional incentive structures for recognising and rewarding FAIR data management practices at Danish universities
2. Align our work on recognising and rewarding FAIR research outputs with the activities in the national CoARA chapter
3. Contribute actively to the activities in the national CoARA chapter

Actions:

1. Conduct structured interviews with relevant stakeholders to clarify where and how FAIR research outputs are currently recognised at Danish research institutions
2. Map activities at the eight Danish universities regarding CoARA engagement
3. Reach out to the CoARA National Chapter Denmark and offer expertise on assessing FAIR data outputs
4. Refine the tools developed at the DeiC Conference 2025 workshop (policy snippets, minimum FAIR eligibility bar, checklists, and rubric), for example through community co-creation

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

1. Milestone M3.1 (June 2026): Mapping of university CoARA engagement completed; contact established with CoARA National Chapter Denmark; stakeholder interviews initiated
2. Milestone M3.2 (September 2026): Stakeholder interviews completed; refined tools prepared for community feedback
3. Milestone M3.3 (November 2026): Overview of results in a report to the FAIR Reference Group

10. Goals & actions: working group F

Valuation of data

Working Group F has developed proposals for actions addressing the following focus areas:

Focus area 13

What criteria for a dynamic value of data as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context are applied by local, national, and international organisations to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

Goals:

After the first year of the mandate period, the working group postponed certain tasks and goals to year two. The overarching goal of Working Group F this year is to deliver a self-contained and final result by the end of the mandate period, while still providing recommendations for further work and development.

The goals for 2026 are:

Goal A: Conduct comprehensive stakeholder interviews with representatives from Research, System administration, Research foundations, Research management and policy, and Archival institutions.

Goal B: Develop a foundational framework for the value of data.

Goal C: Develop recommendations for follow-up actions to implement the framework

Goal D: Produce a report showcasing how data valuation informs research data management processes and how stakeholders envision the proposed framework adding value to these processes.

Goal E: Based on the conceptual framework, develop a proof of concept for an ontology for the concept of data value to support tools for assessing data value. This will be a first initial seed implementation for later development.

Actions:

Working Group F will undertake the following activities to achieve the goals for 2026:

Goal A: Define and describe a comprehensive interview guide, and conduct stakeholder interviews. Stakeholders have been identified by leveraging knowledge from Working Group F members, Chairpersons of Working Groups A through D, and The FAIR Reference Group.

Goals B and D: Analyse and synthesise the interviews to inform the Framework and the end-of-year report. This includes examining how the value of data shapes data management decisions and processes at the universities, and how interviewees perceive the framework as adding value to those processes. Publish the Framework on Zenodo by end of year.

Goal D: Perform online research on selected international organisations in countries such as Australia, the Netherlands, Austria, and the United Kingdom. In addition, contacts acquired during International Data Week 2025 in Brisbane will be used. If relevant, short online interviews will be held with key persons behind these international data value related activities.

Goal C: Based on the Framework and results from the interviews, create recommendations for follow-up actions to implement the Framework. During the interviews, use cases and personas will be gathered and used in the report as examples of implementation recommendations.

Goal E: Create a first version of an ontology for describing and assessing the value of a data collection. This will be done using Web Ontology Language (OWL) and will serve as an initial seed for further development and discussion.

Monitoring progress, including a timeline:

Action	Estimated completion
Complete all national interviews (Goal A)	June
Analysis and synthesis of interviews (Goal B and D)	September
Online investigation of select international organisations, and where relevant, short online interviews (Goal D)	October
Publish a seed version of an ontology using OWL in GitHub (Goal E)	November
Publish the report for 2026 (Goal D) including <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The Framework (Goal B)• Recommendation (Goal C)	November

11. Concluding notes

The FAIR Reference group and working groups acknowledge that there may be overlap in the activities and will work towards effective coordination among the working groups and their focus areas. It is also recognised that the same topics can be addressed from different perspectives. Effective coordination among the chairpersons of the working groups will ensure that the focus areas are well covered from various perspectives, while avoiding too much repetition, and leaving room for potential synergies.